

D3.1 Kinetic and electrochemical model

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Executive summary

The deliverable reports on the progress in the development of a kinetic and electrochemical model. Kinetics of the reaction sequence over the electrode are described by atomistic modelling and implemented as input parameters in the electrochemical model. In the electrochemical model, the current-potential relation is given a generic analytical expression adaptable to all applications relying on electrochemical conversion and transport of protons over a solid electrolyte. This model is under development, meaning that it incorporates kinetic parameters, but still needs an analytical solution to incorporate the effect of voltage on the reaction rates. We therefore also derive a semi-analytical solution, where measured resistances at increasing voltage is used to derive a current-voltage relation over the electrode. An atomistic modelling approach using Density Functional Theory (DFT) is being developed for calculating material specific rate parameters, including energy barriers $E_{a(i)}$ and pre-exponential factors $A^0_{(i)}$, for migration, diffusion, and (electro)chemical reactions. Significant progress has been made, where we can now readily determine the kinetic parameters for, e.g., bulk and surface diffusion, adsorption, dissociation, and chemical reactions. However, there is still progress to be made on how to properly describe the charge transfer associated with electrochemical conversion, and the plethora of different potentials $\mu_{(i)}$, ϕ , etc. The DFT approach is applied to the triple-phase boundaries in the Ni-BZCYO cermet system, which is relevant for hydrogen pumping. This is a well-studied and chemically "simple" model system, which makes it highly suitable for developing and testing the DFT approach. In the electrochemical model, the first step is to define the various energy contributions, how equilibrium is established at Open Circuit Voltage (OCV), and how chemical equilibrium is shifted by a deviation of the electrostatic potential ($\Delta\phi$) from OCV (current (I) is running). The relation between $\Delta\phi$ and I constitutes the overpotential (η). The η - I relation is given by the limitations across the electrodes' (positrode and negatrode) reaction coordinates, given by rate- and diffusion expressions. These expressions will be parameterized by $\mu_{(i)}$, $A^0_{(i)}$ and $E_{a(i)}$ and constitute the polarisation resistance. In order to link IV-relations in real systems - under realistic process conditions - to the IV-relations studied and parameterized over model electrodes with defined geometries, the model must incorporate all charge carriers that contribute to the total current under the given thermal and atmospheric conditions. The model is developed and fitted to impedance measurements under positive, zero and negative bias at high temperatures, symmetrical atmosphere (zero chemical gradient) and low p_{H_2O} , where the electrolyte is only partially hydrated. The electrochemical model therefore incorporates transport of protons, oxide ions and electron holes and extract the selectivity for each charge carrier over the assembly of electrodes and electrolyte. Furthermore, the model incorporates the effect of process parameters, allowing the model to be applied also under real process conditions. Here, we present interpretations of how polarisation resistance (R_p) depends on DC bias, and give a general conversion of I - R_p to I - η , enabling a semi-analytical I - U model.

Contents

1	Introduction.....	4
1.1	Presentation of WINNER.....	4
1.2	Scope of the deliverable.....	5
2	Atomistic modelling.....	5
2.1	Objective.....	5
2.2	Introduction to the atomistic modelling.....	6
2.2.1	Structural optimization.....	6
2.2.2	Electronic structure calculations.....	7
2.2.3	Transition state theory.....	7
2.2.4	Lattice dynamics and rate constants.....	8
2.3	Case 1: Ni-BZO cermet for hydrogen pumping.....	9
2.3.1	DFT model system.....	9
2.3.2	Identifying the reaction steps at the TPB.....	9
2.3.3	Current progress.....	11
2.4	Case 2: Pd-BZO cermet for hydrogen pumping.....	16
2.4.1	DFT model system.....	16
2.4.2	Identifying the reaction steps at the TPB.....	17
2.4.3	Current progress.....	17
2.5	Further work.....	22
3	Electrochemical model.....	22

1 Introduction

1.1 Presentation of WINNER

The WINNER project aims to develop an efficient and durable technology platform based on electrochemical proton conducting ceramic (PCC) cells designed for unlocking a path towards commercially viable production, extraction, purification and compression of hydrogen at small to medium scale. This will be demonstrated in WINNER in three applications: ammonia cracking, dehydrogenation of hydrocarbons, and reversible steam electrolysis. By such, WINNER will create innovative solutions for flexible, secure and profitable storage and utilization of energy in the form of hydrogen and green ammonia, electrification of the chemical industry and sectors coupling.

The WINNER project builds on the pioneering multidisciplinary expertise of world leading partners in the fields of proton conducting ceramic (PCC) materials and technologies to combine materials science, multi-scale multi-physics modelling and advanced in-situ and operando characterisation methods to unveil unprecedented performance of tubular PCC cells assembled in a flexible multi-tube module operating at industrially relevant conditions. WINNER will develop innovative cell architectures with multifunctional electrodes and a novel pressure-less current collection system using eco-friendly and scalable manufacturing routes.

Figure 1 WINNER concept focusing on novel materials, electrodes, current collection, and assemblies for three main applications

The experimental activities will be steered by a novel multi-scale multi-physics modelling platform and enhanced experimentation methodologies. These tools combined with advanced operando and in situ methods will serve at establishing correlations between performance and degradation mechanisms associated with both materials properties and interface's evolution upon operation. Testing of cells and modules will also be conducted to define performance and durability in various operation modes. Techno-economic assessment of the novel PCC processes will be conducted as well as Life Cycle Assessment. The project is coordinated by SINTEF with support from University of Oslo, Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas (CSIC-ITQ), Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU), Aktiebolaget Sandvik Materials Technology, CoorsTek Membrane Sciences AS, ENGIE, Shell Global Solutions International B.V.

1.2 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable reports on the progress in developing an analytical solution relating the $I - U - \eta_{pol} - Rp$ for total and individual electrochemical processes affecting the overall cell performance under OCV and biases. Here we use atomistic modelling of kinetic rate parameters for the individual electrode reaction steps on a Ni-BaZrO₃ interface, and the results from Impedance Spectroscopy, relating the current-overpotential ($I-\eta$) characteristics for individual reaction steps on a Ba_{0.5}La_{0.5}CoO₃ (BLC) oxide electrode. The results represent a significant step forward in finding a link between modelled parameters, kinetic rate expression under OCV and biases and cell overpotentials.

2 Atomistic modelling

2.1 Objective

The atomistic modelling is performed in the framework of density functional theory (DFT), where the calculations aim at providing material specific rate parameters as inputs to the electrochemical model. The two most important output parameters from the DFT calculations include:

- **$Ea_{(i,j)}$** : Energy barrier for a specific transport/reaction step, determined by the nudged elastic band (NEB) method. Ea over reaction step i for charge carrier j should include contributions from enthalpy and entropy, and zero point energy (ZPE) contributions.
- **$A^0_{(i,j)}$** : Pre-exponential factor, which can be interpreted as a characteristic “attempt frequency”. $A^0_{(i,j)}$ is described by the difference in the vibrational properties of the moving specie at the transition state and the initial state.

A robust DFT methodology for describing these kinetic parameters is being developed in WINNER. The methodology will be material universal and transferable to most electrochemical processes. It should be applicable to bulk, surfaces, and interfaces, for both single-material and heterostructures.

2.2 Introduction to the atomistic modelling

The workflow used for the DFT calculations performed in WINNER is shown schematically in Figure 2. Figure 2a describes the workflow for structural optimization, while Figure 2b summarizes the most relevant material specific properties calculated by DFT in WINNER; electronic structure, transition state theory, and lattice dynamics.

Figure 2. Flow charts showing the working principle for running DFT calculations, which includes a) structural optimization and b) calculating different material specific properties.

2.2.1 Structural optimization

The most computationally time-consuming process is typically the structural optimization in Figure 2a. An input atomic structure is supplied, and the energy and atomic forces are evaluated. If the forces on all the atoms are below a set threshold value, the atomic structure is deemed converged. On the other hand, if the forces are above the threshold value, the atomic structure is updated according to the calculated forces, and the energy and forces of the updated atomic structure is evaluated. This iterative process of updating the structure and evaluating the forces is repeated until convergence is reached. Once convergence is reached, the output atomic structure and corresponding forces and energetics, are used for post-processing and further analysis (Figure 2b).

2.2.2 Electronic structure calculations

Electronic properties of bulk, surfaces, and interfaces, and how these change across the transport path(s) are determined by calculated electronic density of states (DOS), Bader charge analysis, and electrostatic potentials. These calculations provide fundamental insights into band gaps, effective masses, charge compensation and (de)localization, work functions, electric potentials etc.

2.2.3 Transition state theory

The energy barrier for specific transport/reaction steps (also referred to as a jump) are evaluated through transition state theory. The minimum energy path (MEP) for the transport process is determined by the climbing image nudged elastic band (ci-NEB) method. The method involves performing structural optimizations for intermediate atomic structures (here referred to as intermediate images) between two fixed configurations, while adding restrictions to the optimization to prevent the intermediate images to relax back to the (lower energy) initial or final states. The highest energy image is located at the saddle point, and the MEP should give an accurate description of the 0 K energy barrier for the transport path. As an example, Figure 3 shows the DFT calculated MEP for the migration of a proton in the bulk of BaZrO₃, with a 0 K energy barrier of 0.27 eV.

Figure 3. Calculated minimum energy path (MEP) for the migration of a proton in undoped BaZrO₃. Vibrational excitation energies $h\nu_i$ along the migration path are indicated by the grey horizontal lines.

The energy barrier $Ea_{(i)}$ at finite temperature to be input in the electrochemical model is given by

$$Ea_{(i,j)} = \Delta E_{mig} + \Delta ZPE - T\Delta S_{vib}$$

where ΔE_{mig} is the calculated 0 K migration energy barrier, ΔZPE is the difference in zero point energy (ZPE) between the transition state and the initial state, and ΔS_{vib} is the difference in the vibrational

entropy between the transition state and the initial state. The two latter properties are described further below.

2.2.4 Lattice dynamics and rate constants

The vibrational properties are determined within the harmonic approximation, where the atomic vibrational frequencies are obtained from the finite displacement method. In WINNER, the lattice dynamics are used to calculate the pre-exponential factors ($A^0_{(i,j)}$), entropies (S), and zero point energies (ZPE).

The pre-exponential factor, $A^0_{(i,j)}$, at finite temperature T is defined as

$$A^0_{(i,j)} = \frac{k_B T}{h} \frac{\prod_{i,j}^N (1 - e^{h\nu_{i,j}/k_B T})}{\prod_{i,j}^{N-1} (1 - e^{h\nu^*_{i,j}/k_B T})}$$

where $\nu_{i,j}$ and $\nu^*_{i,j}$ are the vibrational frequencies for the initial state and transition states, respectively, k_B the Boltzmann constant, and h the Planck's constant. $A^0_{(i,j)}$ can be interpreted as a characteristic "attempt frequency" for the transport process.

The vibrational entropy, S_{vib} , of the atomic species are given by

$$S_{vib} = k_B \sum_{i,j} \left(\frac{\beta_{i,j}}{\exp(\beta_{i,j}) - 1} - \ln(1 - \exp(-\beta_{i,j})) \right)$$

where $\beta_{i,j} = h\nu_{i,j}/k_B T$.

ZPE corrections account for the finite energy of a quantum system at 0 K, and is defined as

$$\text{ZPE} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i h\nu_i$$

As a first approximation, the rate constant for a transport step (i) can be calculated by

$$k_{(i)} = A^0_{(i)} \exp\left(-\frac{Ea_{(i)}}{k_B T}\right)$$

which can be used to determine the rate-limiting step across a specific modelled charge transport path (*i.e.*, a chain of multiple migration steps).

2.3 Case 1: Ni-BZO cermet for hydrogen pumping

To develop and test the DFT methodology, we choose the Ni-BZCYO cermet as the first case, which is relevant for hydrogen pumping. This is a well-studied and chemically "simple model" system, which makes it highly suitable for developing and testing of the methodology. Figure 4 shows a 2D schematic for possible interactions and transport processes of hydrogen at the different regions of the electrode-electrolyte heterostructure, including bulk diffusion, surface reaction and diffusion, double-phase boundary (DPB) reactions, and triple-phase boundary (TPB) reactions. For now, the focus is mainly on the TPB interactions.

Figure 4. 2D schematic of possible interactions/transport processes for hydrogen in bulk, surfaces, DPB, and TPB for an electrode-electrolyte heterostructure.

2.3.1 DFT model system

The Ni-BZCYO cermet is modelled as a heterostructure of Ni and undoped BaZrO₃ (BZO). The DFT model system is shown in Figure 5. It consists of a 10 atoms large Ni particle ((111) surface towards vacuum, (001) towards BZO) on top of a symmetric BaO-terminated slab (7 atomic layer thick, 4x4 unit cells in the *ab*-plane), with a 25 Å vacuum region between the BaO-surfaces (total of 282 atoms). The specific model system size has been chosen as a compromise between computational resource cost, accuracy, and experimental relevance.

2.3.2 Identifying the reaction steps at the TPB

The hydrogen transport across the TPB in the Ni-BZO cermet can be described by the following seven reaction steps, as illustrated in Figure 5.

1. The dissociation of H₂ (g) to adsorbed hydrogen on the Ni surface ($H_{Ni,ads}$) can occur through one or two steps according to (in Kröger-Vink notation)

2. Diffusion of $\text{H}_{\text{Ni,ads}}$ on the Ni surface

3. Electrochemical conversion hydrogen from the Ni electrode to protons in the BZO electrolyte surface (OH_0^\bullet)

4. Incorporation of the proton from the BZO surface to the BZO TPB subsurface

5. Sub-surface diffusion of protons in BZO

6. Sub-sub-surface diffusion of protons in BZO

7. Bulk diffusion of protons in BZO

To speed up the process, reaction steps 1, 2, and 7 can be calculated separately for the different materials (Ni for 1 and 2, BaZrO_3 for 5), while reaction steps 3 to 6 must be calculated for the heterostructure system.

Figure 5. DFT model system for describing the hydrogen transport across the TPB in the Ni-BZO cermet. Note that the entire BZO slab is not shown, for simplicity.

2.3.3 Current progress

2.3.3.1 Reaction step 1: Dissociation of H₂ (g)

The dissociation of H₂ (g) on a Ni(111) surface in reaction step 1 is calculated on a 7 layer thick $p(4 \times 4)$ Ni(111) slab. Currently, we have obtained results for the dissociation of adsorbed H₂ molecule, corresponding to the second step for the two-step process described above: $H_{2,ads} = 2H_{ads}$. The initial, transition state, and final atomic configurations are shown in Figure 6(a). The corresponding MEP is shown in Figure 6(b), with a 0 K dissociation energy barrier of $\Delta E_{dis} = 0.08$ eV. The energy barrier including ZPE and entropy contributions is $Ea_{(i,j)} = -0.12$ eV at 873 K. The pre-exponential factor is $A^0_{(i,j)} = 1.9$ ps⁻¹ at 873 K. Since the activation energy barrier is negative, this means that the dissociation will be spontaneous once the H₂ molecule is adsorbed on the surface. In practice, we can thus assume that the adsorbed H₂ molecule itself is the transition state between H₂ (g) and H_{ads}, as presumed for Pd-BZO below. This will be implemented also for the Ni-BZO system.

Figure 6. Calculated a) atomic configurations, and b) corresponding MEP for the dissociation step $H_{2,ads} = 2H_{ads}$. Vibrational excitation energies $h\nu_i$ along the reaction path are indicated by the grey horizontal lines.

2.3.3.2 Reaction step 2: Surface diffusion of H on Ni(111)

Figure 7 shows the calculated atomic configuration (a) and corresponding MEP (b) for the surface diffusion of an adsorbed hydrogen atom on the Ni(111) surface according to reaction step 2: $H_{ads} = H_{ads}$. The 0 K migration barrier is $\Delta E_{mig,H} = 0.14$ eV. The energy barrier is $Ea_{(mig,H)} = 0.19$ eV at 873 K, and the pre-exponential factor is $A^0_{(mig,H)} = 1.18 \times 10^{13}$ s⁻¹ at 873 K.

Figure 7. Calculated a) atomic configurations, and b) corresponding MEP for the surface diffusion $H_{ads} = H_{ads}$. Vibrational excitation energies $h\nu_i$ along the reaction path are indicated by the grey horizontal lines.

2.3.3.3 Reaction step 3: Electrochemical conversion at the TPB

Figure 8(a) shows the preliminary results for the structural relaxation of hydrogen adsorbed either on the Ni (left) or BZO (right) side of the TPB, corresponding to the electrochemical conversion step: $H_{Ni,TPB} = OH_{O,TPB}^{\bullet} + e'$. The corresponding relative energies for the two configurations are shown in Figure 8(b). Note, however, that these are preliminary results, and the final relative energies might change after convergence is reached. Further note that the transition state energy – determining $Ea_{(tpb,H)}$ – is expected to be higher in energy than the two end-members.

Figure 8. Calculated (a) atomic configurations, and (b) corresponding energy difference between the initial and final state for the electrochemical conversion step $H_{Ni,TPB} = OH_{O,TPB}^{\bullet} + e'$. Note that these are preliminary results, and that the TS is expected to be higher in energy than the two end-members.

2.3.3.4 Reaction step 4: Incorporation of the BZO surface proton

Figure 9(a) shows the preliminary results for the structural relaxation of hydrogen adsorbed on the BZO surface at the TPB (left) and after incorporation in the BZO subsurface (right), corresponding to the absorption step: $OH_{O,TPB}^{\bullet} = OH_{O,sub}^{\bullet}$. The corresponding relative energies for the two configurations are shown in Figure 9(b). Note, however, that these are preliminary results, and the final relative energies might change after convergence is reached. Further note that the transition – determining $Ea_{(inc,H)}$ – state is expected to be higher in energy than the two end-members.

Figure 9. Calculated (a) atomic configurations, and (b) corresponding energy difference between the initial and final state for the absorption of BZO surface proton $\text{OH}_{\text{O,TPB}}^{\bullet} = \text{OH}_{\text{O,TPB-sub}}^{\bullet}$. Note that these are preliminary results, and that the TS is expected to be higher in energy than the two end-members.

2.3.3.5 Reaction step 5: Sub-surface diffusion of protons in BZO

Figure 10(a) shows the preliminary results for the structural relaxation of hydrogen in the TPB subsurface (left) and in the BZO subsurface (right), corresponding to the absorption step: $\text{OH}_{\text{O,TPB-sub}}^{\bullet} = \text{OH}_{\text{O,sub-1}}^{\bullet}$. The corresponding relative energies for the two configurations are shown in Figure 10(b). Note, however, that these are preliminary results, and the final relative energies might change after convergence is reached. Further note that the transition – determining $E_{a(\text{sub1,H})}$ – state is expected to be higher in energy than the two end-members.

Figure 10. Calculated (a) atomic configurations, and (b) corresponding energy difference between the initial and final state for the sub-surface proton diffusion $\text{OH}_{\text{O,TPB-sub}}^{\bullet} = \text{OH}_{\text{O,sub-1}}^{\bullet}$. Nota that there are preliminary results, and that the TS is expected to be higher in energy than the two end-members.

2.3.3.6 Reaction step 6: Sub-sub-surface diffusion of protons in BZO

Figure 11(a) shows the preliminary results for the structural relaxation of hydrogen in the BZO sub-surface (left) and BZO sub-sub-surface (right), corresponding to the absorption step: $\text{OH}_{\text{O,sub-1}}^{\bullet} = \text{OH}_{\text{O,sub-2}}^{\bullet}$. The corresponding relative energies for the two configurations are shown in Figure 11(b). Note, however, that these are preliminary results, and the final relative energies might change after

convergence is reached. Further note that the transition – determining $Ea_{(sub2,H)}$ – state is expected to be higher in energy than the two end-members.

Figure 11. Calculated (a) atomic configurations, and (b) corresponding energy difference between the initial and final state for the sub-surface proton diffusion $OH_{O,sub-1}^* = OH_{O,sub-2}^*$. Nota that there are preliminary results, and that the TS is expected to be higher in energy than the two end-members.

2.3.3.7 Reaction step 7: Bulk diffusion of protons in BZO

The calculated atomic configuration and corresponding MEP for bulk diffusion of protons in BZO are shown in Figure 12a and b, respectively. The MEP has a 0 K migration energy of $\Delta E_{mig} = 0.27$ eV. The migration energy barrier at 873 K is $Ea_{(bulk,H)} = 0.23$ eV, with a pre-exponential factor of $A^0_{(bulk,H)} = 1.10 \times 10^{13} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Figure 12. Calculated (a) atomic configurations, and (b) corresponding MEP for the bulk diffusion $OH_0^* = OH_0^*$. Vibrational excitation energies $h\nu_i$ along the reaction path are indicated by the grey horizontal lines.

2.3.3.8 Summary

The currently obtained dissociation/migration barriers ΔE , activation energies $Ea_{(i,j)}$ and pre-exponential factors $A^0_{(i,j)}$ for the different reaction steps at 873 K are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of calculated 0 K dissociation/migration energy barriers ΔE , and energy barriers $Ea_{(i,j)}$ and pre-exponential factors $A^0_{(i,j)}$ at 873 K.

Reaction step	ΔE (eV)	$Ea_{(i,j)}$ (eV)*	$A^0_{(i,j)}$ (ps ⁻¹)*
1. $H_{2,ads} = 2H_{Ni,ads}$	0.08	-0.12	1.9
2. $H_{Ni,ads} = H_{Ni,ads}$	0.14	0.19	11.8
3. $H_{Ni,TPB} = OH_{O,TPB} + e'$	0.84**		
4. $OH_{O,surf} = OH_{O,TPB-sub}$	0.78**		
5. $OH_{O,TPB-sub} = OH_{O,sub-1}$	0.27**		
6. $OH_{O,sub-1} = OH_{O,sub-2}$	0.14**		
5. $OH_{O} = OH_{O}$	0.27	0.23	11.0

*Evaluated at 873 K.

**Energy differences between initial and final configurations only.

Assuming that the end configuration for each reaction step is equal in energy as the initial configuration for the next reaction step, the relative 0 K energy landscape can be calculated as shown in Figure 13. These results indicate that the charge transfer step is the energetically most costly. Note, however, that relative energies during the electrochemical conversion step, involving the conversion of a neutral hydrogen on the Ni-surface to a proton in BaZrO₃, is not clearly defined within the DFT community. We are currently discussing how to properly treat this electrochemical conversion step on a fundamental level.

Figure 13. Calculated relative 0 K energy landscape for reaction step 1 to 5 from the MEP in Figure 6 to Figure 12.

2.4 Case 2: Pd-BZO cermet for hydrogen pumping

The developed methodology has in parallel been applied to the Pd-BZO cermet system. The system is qualitatively similar to the Ni-BZO cermet, where the two metals show comparable activities towards hydrogen dissociation, adsorption, and surface diffusion. Due to the better lattice-mismatch between Pd(001) and BZO(001), the modeled Pd particle shows less deformation compared to Ni, and thus converges in fewer ionic steps during structural optimization. Furthermore, Pd is non-metallic, which significantly reduces the computation time compared to metallic materials. Hence, even though Pd-BZO system is not of explicitly experimentally relevant to the project, it is a good material candidate to obtain results more rapidly to qualitatively test the methodology during development, and with expected comparable results to the Ni-BZO system.

2.4.1 DFT model system

The system is modelled similarly as the Ni-BZO system described in Figure 14 and summarized as follows:

- 10 atoms large Pd particle ((001) terminated towards BZO, (111) towards vacuum)
- 7 atomic layer thick symmetric BaO-terminated slab (4x4 unit cells in the ab -plane), with a 25 Å vacuum region between the BaO-surfaces (total of 282 atoms).

The adsorption and diffusion on Pd(111) has been modelled using a 7 layer thick $p(4 \times 4)$ slab as described for Ni(111) above.

Figure 14. DFT model system for describing the hydrogen transport across the TPB in the Pd-BZO cermet.

2.4.2 Identifying the reaction steps at the TPB

The hydrogen transport across the TPB in the Pd-BZO cermet can be described by the following 8 reaction steps, as illustrated in Figure 14:

1. The dissociation of H_2 (g) to adsorbed hydrogen on the Pd surface (H_{Pd}) is modelled through a two-step process according to (in Kröger-Vink notation)

2. Diffusion of $H_{Pd,ads}$ on the Pd(111) surface

3. Diffusion of $H_{Pd,ads}$ to the TPB

4. Electrochemical conversion hydrogen from the Pd electrode to protons in the BZO electrolyte surface (OH_O)

5. Incorporation of the proton from the BZO surface to the BZO TPB subsurface

6. Sub-surface diffusion of protons in BZO

7. Sub-sub-surface diffusion of protons in BZO

8. Bulk diffusion of protons in BZO

2.4.3 Current progress

2.4.3.1 Reaction step 1: Dissociation of H_2 (g)

The preliminary calculated atomic configuration and corresponding MEP for the dissociation of molecular H_2 adsorbed on Pd(111) are shown in FIG Xa and b, respectively. The dissociation shows no migration energy barrier at 0 K, *i.e.*, $\Delta E_{mig} < 0$ eV. The migration energy barrier $Ea_{(diss,H_2)}$ and pre-exponential factor of $A_{(diss,H_2)}^0$ will be determined once the NEB calculation is converged.

Figure 15. Calculated a) atomic configurations, and b) corresponding MEP for the dissociation step $H_{2,ads} = 2H_{ads}$.

The activation energy barrier for the dissociation is negative, which means that this process will be spontaneous once the H_2 molecule is adsorbed on the surface. Since the H_2 adsorption shows a positive Gibbs free energy ($E_{a(i)}$) reported in Table 2 equals the Gibbs formation energy of $H_{2,ads}$ per H atom), we assume that the adsorbed H_2 molecule acts as a transition state between H_2 (g) and H_{ads} . This assumption has been used to describe the total energy profile in Figure 22.

2.4.3.2 Reaction step 2: Surface diffusion of H on Pd(111)

The calculated atomic configuration and corresponding MEP for the surface diffusion of H on Pd(111) are shown in Figure 16a and b, respectively. The MEP has a 0 K migration energy of $\Delta E_{mig} = 0.15$ eV.

The migration energy barrier at 673 K is $E_{a(sub1,H)} = 0.19$ eV, with a pre-exponential factor of $A^0_{(sub1,H)} = 1.00 \times 10^{13} s^{-1}$.

Figure 16. Calculated a) atomic configurations, and b) corresponding MEP for the surface diffusion of H on Pd(111), $H_{Pd,ads} = H_{Pd,ads}$. Vibrational excitation energies $h\nu_i$ along the reaction path are indicated by the grey horizontal lines.

2.4.3.3 Reaction step 3: Diffusion of H from Pd(111) to the TPB

The calculated atomic configuration and corresponding MEP for the surface diffusion of H from Pd(111) to the TPB are shown in Figure 17a and b, respectively. The MEP has a 0 K migration energy of $\Delta E_{mig} = 0.09$ eV.

The migration energy barrier at 673 K is $E_{a(bulk,H)} = 0.12$ eV, with a pre-exponential factor of $A^0_{(Pd,TPB,H)} = 9.84 \times 10^{12} s^{-1}$.

Figure 17. Calculated a) atomic configurations, and b) corresponding MEP for the surface diffusion of H to the TPB, $H_{Pd,ads} = H_{Pd,TPB}$. Vibrational excitation energies $h\nu_i$ along the reaction path are indicated by the grey horizontal lines.

2.4.3.4 Reaction step 4: Electrochemical conversion at the TPB

The calculated atomic configuration and corresponding MEP for the electrochemical conversion at the TPB are shown in Figure 18a and b, respectively. The MEP has a 0 K migration energy of $\Delta E_{mig} = 0.94$ eV.

The migration energy barrier at 673 K is $Ea_{(tpb,H)} = 0.89$ eV, with a pre-exponential factor of $A^0_{(tpb,H)} = 2.30 \times 10^{13} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Figure 18. Calculated a) atomic configurations, and b) corresponding MEP for the electrochemical conversion hydrogen from the Pd electrode to protons in the BZO electrolyte surface, $H_{Pd,TPB} = OH_{O,TPB} + e'$. Vibrational excitation energies $h\nu_i$ along the reaction path are indicated by the grey horizontal lines.

2.4.3.5 Reaction step 5: Incorporation of the BZO surface proton

The calculated atomic configuration and corresponding MEP for the incorporation of the BZO surface proton are shown in Figure 19a and b, respectively. The MEP has a 0 K migration energy of $\Delta E_{mig} = 0.68$ eV.

The migration energy barrier at 673 K is $Ea_{(inc,H)} = 0.67$ eV, with a pre-exponential factor of $A^0_{(inc,H)} = 5.82 \times 10^{12} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Figure 19. Calculated a) atomic configurations, and b) corresponding MEP for the incorporation of the proton from the BZO surface to the BZO TPB subsurface, $OH_{O,TPB} = OH_{O,TPB-sub}$. Vibrational excitation energies $h\nu_i$ along the reaction path are indicated by the grey horizontal lines.

2.4.3.6 Reaction step 6: Sub-surface diffusion of protons in BZO

The calculated atomic configuration and corresponding MEP for the sub-surface diffusion of protons in BZO are shown in Figure 20a and b, respectively. The MEP has a 0 K migration energy of $\Delta E_{mig} = 0.09$ eV.

The migration energy barrier at 673 K is $Ea_{(sub1,H)} = 0.08$ eV, with a pre-exponential factor of $A^0_{(sub1,H)} = 1.38 \times 10^{13} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Figure 20. Calculated a) atomic configurations, and b) corresponding MEP for the sub-surface diffusion of protons in BZO, $OH_{O,TBP-sub} = OH_{O,sub-1}$. Vibrational excitation energies $h\nu_i$ along the reaction path are indicated by the grey horizontal lines.

2.4.3.7 Reaction step 7: Sub-sub-surface diffusion of protons in BZO

The calculated atomic configuration and corresponding MEP for the sub-sub-surface diffusion of protons in BZO are shown in Figure 21a and b, respectively. The MEP has a 0 K migration energy of $\Delta E_{mig} = 0.05$ eV.

The migration energy barrier at 673 K is $Ea_{(sub2,H)} = 0.05$ eV, with a pre-exponential factor of $A^0_{(sub2,H)} = 1.19 \times 10^{13} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Figure 21. Calculated a) atomic configurations, and b) corresponding MEP for the sub-surface diffusion of protons in BZO, $OH_{O,sub-1} = OH_{O,sub-2}$. Vibrational excitation energies $h\nu_i$ along the reaction path are indicated by the grey horizontal lines.

2.4.3.8 Reaction step 8: Bulk diffusion of protons in BZO

The bulk diffusion of protons in BZO is equal to that in Section 2.3.3.7. Note that the configurations $OH_{O,sub-3}$ shows a slightly lower energy than the configurations $OH_{O,sub-2}$ and $OH_{O,sub-4}$. This arises as an artifact of the DFT model system, where the first proton is bonded to oxygen parallel to the BZO(001) surface, while the two latter are bonded to oxygen perpendicular to the surface, which imposes some difference in defect-defect and defect-surface interactions. For clarity, the bulk diffusion is thus calculated in bulk supercells only.

2.4.3.9 Summary

Figure 22 shows the calculated formation Gibbs energy of the hydrogen/proton defect relative to H_2 (g) at 673 K across the charge transport process. The transition state energies calculated using ci-NEB are marked by "TS". The corresponding energy barriers $Ea_{(i)}$ and pre-exponential factors $A_{(i)}^0$ for the different steps are summarized in Table 2. The current results suggest that the rate limiting step is the charge transfer step across the interface between Pd and BZO.

Figure 22. Calculated Gibbs formation energy for the H or H^+ defect relative to H_2 (g) at 673 K for the charge carrier transport across the Pd-BZO TPB illustrated in Figure 14.

Table 2. Calculated energy barriers $Ea_{(i)}$, pre-exponential factors $A_{(i)}^0$, and rate constants $k_{(i)}$ at 673 K for the different charge carrier transport steps across the phase boundary in the Pd-BZO cermet system.

Step.	$Ea_{(i)}$ (eV)	$A_{(i)}^0$ (s^{-1})	$k_{(i)}$ (s^{-1})
1. $\frac{1}{2}H_2(g) \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}H_{2,Pd} \rightarrow H_{Pd}$	0.14	–	–
2. $H_{Pd} \rightarrow H_{Pd}$	0.19	1.00×10^{13}	3.82×10^{11}
3. $H_{Pd} \rightarrow H_{Pd,TPB}$	0.12	9.84×10^{12}	1.22×10^{12}
4. $H_{Pd,TPB} \rightarrow OH_{O,TPB}$	0.89	2.30×10^{13}	5.20×10^6
5. $OH_{O,TPB} \rightarrow OH_{O,TPB-sub}^{\bullet}$	0.67	5.82×10^{12}	5.17×10^7
6. $OH_{O,TPB-sub}^{\bullet} \rightarrow OH_{O,sub-1}^{\bullet}$	0.08	1.38×10^{13}	3.68×10^{12}
7. $OH_{O,sub-1}^{\bullet} \rightarrow OH_{O,sub-2}^{\bullet}$	0.05	1.19×10^{13}	5.16×10^{12}
8. $OH_{O}^{\bullet} \rightarrow OH_{O}$	0.20	9.81×10^{12}	3.06×10^{11}

2.5 Further work

We have developed and tested a general atomistic modelling methodology for calculating kinetic parameters for charge carrier transport across interfaces and in bulk based on density functional theory (DFT) calculations. The next step in developing the methodology is to implement the following:

- The effect bias potential has on charge transfer steps
- Diffusion coefficients
- The effect of space-charge region
- Potential change across full anode-electrolyte-cathode systems.

Note that there is a plethora of different potentials in an electrochemical system, such as electrochemical potential ($\bar{\mu}_{(i)}$), chemical potential ($\mu_{(i)}$), electrostatic potential (φ), electrode potential (E_{we}), and overpotential (η), that needs to be addressed. We are currently discussing which potentials should be treated by the atomistic modelling, and which by the electrochemical model, and how to properly describe them by the appropriate modelling techniques.

We have recently initiated studies applying the methodology to the BGLC electrode, focusing on the endmembers $BaGdCo_2O_{6-\delta}$ and $BaLaCo_2O_{6-\delta}$. Further research will focus mainly on this material system, and how to combine the results that will be obtained on BGLC (and other electrode systems) with the results for the cermet system described above.

3 Electrochemical model

The aim of the deliverable is to show the development of an electrochemical model with an analytical solution directly relating kinetic parameters to overpotential (η) and current (I) for total and individual

electrochemical processes. Deliverable D1.4 shows the first step of the model employed to extract individual contributions to R_{DC} , partial currents for protons, oxide ions, and electron holes under positive (anodic) and negative (cathodic) DC biases. Partial resistances for individual reaction steps (i) and individual charge carriers (j) are fitted to rate expressions;

$$\frac{1}{R_{p,i,j}} = nFpO_2^{n,i,j} pH_2O^{m,i,j} A_{i,j}^0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_{A,i,j}}{RT}\right) \quad 3.1$$

where materials specific pre-exponential values ($A_{(i)}^0$) and activation energies ($E_{a(i)}$) values are extracted experimentally and will be held together with values from DFT calculations, as explained in section 2. In this section we show how to relate the individual resistances – with accompanying rate expressions – to the current-overpotential ($I-\eta$) characteristics for individual reaction steps. The c -parameter in Eq. 3.1 is a geometrical factor, incorporating concentration of adsorption sites and extension of the reaction zone, z (Figure 23). It is expected that z will be dependent on I , and this dependence will be shown in model electrode studies with defined geometries.

Figure 23: Schematic of the reaction zone with geometrical parameters x , y and z .

If charge transfer is not rate limiting for the electrode reaction, all kinetic steps – like adsorption and electron transfer – are inherently coupled to diffusion, which is given a generic expression for current density (i_{cd}) for charge carrier j :

$$i_{cd,j} = nFflux = nFcD \frac{\partial \mu_j}{\partial z} \quad 3.2$$

The coupled kinetic and diffusion steps must be related through the z -parameter to give equal values, and fitted to the corresponding $R_{p,i,j}$ from the impedance measurements (WP1). The diffusion

coefficient for an individual charge carrier (j), D_j incorporates $Ea_{(mig,j)}$ and $A^0_{(mig,j)}$ from the DFT results in section 2, while the chemical potential difference, $\Delta\mu$ over the reaction zone is the driving force, proportional to the overpotential η .

Having established the relation between kinetic parameters and polarization resistance, R_p must be converted to η and added to the ohmic IR-loss to establish the overall $I-U$ relation. In this section we show how to relate the individual resistances – with accompanying rate expressions – to the current-overpotential ($I-\eta$) characteristics. The studied system – with results transferred from WP1 – is a $Ba_{0.5}La_{0.5}CoO_3$ (BLC) electrode on a $BaZr_{0.4}Ce_{0.4}Y_{0.2}O_3$ (BZCY442) electrolyte.

The $I-R_p$ relation is indicative for the nature of the individual process. This relation must therefore be analysed. When ohms law applies – like in a diffusion regime – R_p may be unaffected by increasing bias (linear increase of I with increasing bias). If a charge transfer step (CT) is rate-limiting, R_p will decrease with increasing bias (exponentially increasing I with increasing bias) and if certain types of mass transfer – like gas diffusion – is the limiting step, R_p may increase with increasing bias (static – or limiting – I with increasing bias). Translated from $I-R$ to $I-\eta$, this means that if a CT step is rate limiting, the $I-\eta$ curves will show a Butler- Volmer type of behaviour:

$$I = i_o [\exp(\alpha_a F \eta / RT) - (-\alpha_c F \eta / RT)] \quad 3.3$$

where, α_a and α_c are the charge transfer coefficients under anodic and cathodic biases, i_o is the exchange current density, η is overpotential, F , R , and T have usual meanings. i_o can be calculated by extrapolating the anodic and cathodic Tafel slopes to zero potentials indicating thermally activated exchange current. It is under debate whether mass transfer steps like adsorption or electron transfer will follow B-V behaviour or not.

Figure 24: Effect of applied bias on total and partial R_p 's and measured current (I), (b) Variation of measured current (I) with calculated and integrated overpotential ($\eta_{total, pol}$) for total electrode polarisation, and with integrated overpotentials (η_{pol}) for each reaction step appearing at low frequency (lf), mid frequency (mf) and high frequency (hf) regions of the electrode impedance plots at 650°C in wet air for a BLC electrode.

Figure 24 a shows the variation of the polarisation resistance (R_p) and current with applied bias (U) under anodic and cathodic biases at 650 °C in wet air for a $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{La}_{0.5}\text{CoO}_{3-\delta}$ (BLC) electrode on a BZCY442 electrolyte. BLC is an example of an electrode material with high electron and modest proton conductivity. From Figure 24a, R_p decreases with the increasing anodic bias, and increases with increasing cathodic bias, indicating diminishing effect of anodic bias on R_p – partly also related to increased p -type conductivity in BZCY442 under positive applied potentials. We will not analyse p -type effects at this stage, but rather continue the bias-effect on R_p at lower temperatures where the p -type effect is expected to be negligible. The increase of R_p in cathodic bias indicate an initial activation – or diminishing p -type effect – over the electrode when running the oxygen reduction reaction. It may also reflect partial blocking of oxygen adsorption due to high water or OH coverage.

As the measured DC current is flowing through the whole BLC/BZCY442/Pt system, total η_{pol} was calculated by subtracting the product of current (I) and ohmic (electrolyte) resistance (R_{ohmic}) from the total applied bias (U): $\eta_{pol} = U - IR_{ohmic}$. Partial contributions to η from the electrolyte (ohmic), CT and various diffusion and adsorption steps were found from measured I through their accompanying partial resistances calculated from equivalent circuit modelling of EIS plots. These R 's make up the total R :

$$R = R_{ohmic} + R_{p,hf} + R_{p,mf} + R_{p,lf} \quad 3.4$$

Just like R , U is also composed of the individual contributions over the cell:

$$U = \eta_{ohmic} + \eta_{hf} + \eta_{mf} + \eta_{lf} \quad 3.5$$

η for each reaction step (i) can be calculated from measured I and R_j according to following integration equation:

$$\eta_i = \int_{-I}^I R_{p,i} dI \quad 3.6$$

Figure 24 b shows the variation of total calculated, integrated, and individual polarisation overpotentials (η_{pol}) with measured current (I) at 650 °C in wet air for a BLC electrode on a BZCY442 electrolyte.

Having established the I - η relation in Figure 24 b, we may now present the I - η relation in a tafel plot to extract values for the anodic and cathodic slopes and for i_0 (figure 25).

Figure 25: Tafel plot of $\log(I)$ versus electrode overpotential.

From the tafel plot of $\log(I)$ versus η in figure 25, we see that the overpotential may be roughly expressed and parameterised by a Butler-Volmer type of relation. This indicates that the electrostatic potential (ϕ) of the electrode influences the rate-limiting electrode reaction, either directly – or indirectly through the perturbation of the chemical potential (μ) at the electrode-electrolyte interface. Establishing a I - R - η relation represent a significant progression in the understanding of PCEC electrochemistry and forms a basis for presenting a comprehensive I - U model for the electrochemical cell with input from kinetic modelling and giving output to higher levels in the final engineering model. The next step of electrochemical model is to analyse and parameterise the tafel slopes. By this, the number of electrons in the rate-determining step may be determined. Moreover, assigning the proper mathematical expressions for the I - R p relation will render a potential-term in the rate-expression according to the associated reaction step. The next steps are to evaluate and compare kinetic parameters from DFT and electrochemical modelling in equations 3.1 and 3.2, and moreover to obtain a link between these parameters, process conditions and electrode overpotential as a function of

current. This means introducing terms in equations 3.1 and 3.2, accounting for the electrostatic potential ϕ . This is necessary in order to establish a coherent expression over the two modelling levels (DFT and electrochemistry) and give a final $I-U$ model output to higher modelling levels. At present stage, the model may use measured R_p -values as a function of U or η to transfer the $I-U$ relation for defined electrode materials to higher modelling levels. Furthermore, model electrodes with defined geometry will be studied to obtain the geometrical z component as a function of current.